

“CORPORAL PUNISHMENTS IN SCHOOLS AND ITS EFFECT ON CHILDREN”**Leena**

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Abstract: - Corporal punishment is a violation of the basic human rights of a child. It can be virtually visualized in educational institutions globally either in the form of corporal punishments or physical abuse and as an emotional abuse as well as neglect and also in the different forms of mild or severe sexual abuses. Hosting the world's second-largest education system, and by being the second most populous nation in the world, the problem of corporal punishments cannot be isolated from the country. In educational institutions it exists as an inalienable part of the system. The government has taken initiatives to control it, check it and eradicate it. Various legislations and acts support the mission of the government. However at the level of implementation, it is not much successful in the country. There is not a single law aimed at safeguarding children and protecting them against various forms of corporal punishments, which is a serious lacuna against this background and is needed urgently. This paper will focus on corporal punishments in educational institutions, the laws, legal loopholes, and The Protection of Children against the corporal punishments.

Key Words:-corporal punishment, Neglect, Physical Abuse, Policies, Sexual Abuse,

“Many abused children cling to the hope that growing up will bring escape and freedom. But the personality formed in the environment of coercive control is not well adapted to adult life. The survivor is left with fundamental problems in basic trust, autonomy, and initiative. She approaches the task of early adulthood establishing independence and intimacy burdened by major impairments in self-care, in cognition and in memory, in identity, and in the capacity to form stable relationships. She is still a prisoner of her childhood; attempting to create a new life, she re-counters the drama.

-Judith Lewis Herman, Trauma and Recovery

Introduction

Corporal punishment is used in schools all over the world, despite concern about its effects on children and about the implications for their capacity to benefit from school. At the same time, violence towards children has become a central concern and numerous initiatives are attempting to address it (Save the Children 2012, 2013). One of the success stories in developing countries in the past 15 years has been the increase in enrolment of children in primary schools. However, little attention has been paid to how children experience school, from their viewpoints, and the extent to which corporal punishment is used. Even less attention has been paid to parents' views about their children's experiences at school. Perhaps surprisingly, none of the attention focused on how patriarchy leads to differences in the way

boys and girls are treated at home, at school and in society at large, and the everyday violence that children experience. India is still riddled by huge divisions based on caste, class and socio-economic status, and violence against the powerless by those in power is rampant. This extends to schools, where teachers in a position of power do not hesitate to 'control' children through corporal punishment.

The concept of corporal punishment:-

The United Nations Committee on the Rights of the Child defies corporal punishment as follows: The Committee defies “corporal” or “physical” punishment as any punishment in which physical force is used and intended to cause some degree of pain or discomfort, however light. Most involves hitting (“smacking”, “slapping”, “spanking”) children, with the hand or with an implement – a whip, stick, belt, shoe,

wooden spoon, etc. But it can also involve, for example, kicking, shaking or throwing children, scratching, pinching, biting, pulling hair or boxing ears, forcing children to stay in uncomfortable positions, burning, scalding or forced ingestion (for example, washing children's mouths out with soap or forcing them to swallow hot spices). In the view of the Committee, corporal punishment is invariably degrading. In addition, there are other non-physical forms of punishment that are also cruel and degrading and thus incompatible with the Convention. These include, for example, punishment which belittles, humiliates, denigrates, scapegoats, threatens, scares or ridicules the child. Currently, there is no statutory definition of corporal punishment of children in Indian law. Definition of corporal punishment can at best only be indicative. Children are subject to corporal punishment in schools; institutions meant for care and protection of children such as hostels, orphanages, ashram shalas, and juvenile homes; and even in the family setting. A study 'Child Abuse in India - 2007', by the Ministry of Women and Child Development, Government of India, found that 69% of children reported having been physically abused. Of these 54.68% were boys. Every two out of three school children reported facing corporal punishment. In juvenile justice institutions, 70.21% of children in conflict with the law and 52.86% of children in need of care and protection reported having been physically abuse.

Effects of Corporal Punishment:-

The effect of corporal punishment not only affects the child but also to the parent and the society as a whole.

On Children:- Corporal punishment affects a child both directly and indirectly. It lowers their self-esteem, teaching them poor self-control and promoting negative expectations of themselves and teaches them to be victims. There is a broadly held belief that people who are submitted to corporal punishment are made stronger by it; it "prepares them for life". Today we know that corporal punishment doesn't

make people stronger; rather it makes them more prone to becoming repeat victims. Apart from it, it interferes with the learning process and with their intellectual, sensory and emotional development. It discourages the use of reasoning. By precluding dialogue and reflection, it hampers the capacity to understand the relationship between behavior and its consequences. It makes children feel lonely, sad and abandoned and promotes a negative view of other people and of society as a threatening place. It creates barriers that impede parent-child communication and damages the emotional links established between them and stimulates anger and a desire to run away from home. Violence begets violence. It teaches that violence is an acceptable way of solving problems. Children who have been submitted to corporal punishment may manifest difficulties with social integration. It doesn't teach children to cooperate with authority; it teaches them to comply with the rules or to infringe them. Children can suffer from accidental physical injuries. When someone hits a child, the situation can get out of hand and result in more harm than expected.

On Parents:- The effect of corporal punishment is not only on the child but also on the parents. It can produce feelings of anxiety and guilt, even when the use of this kind of punishment is considered appropriate. The use of corporal punishment increases the probability that parents will show aggressive behavior in the future with growing frequency and intensity and also in other contexts. It inhibits communication and damages the relationship between parents and their children. When parents use corporal punishment because they lack alternative resources, they feel the need to justify their behavior to themselves and to society. So the unease derived from using corporal punishment on children is exacerbated by confused feelings arising from an incoherent and unfounded rationale.

On Society:- Other than the child and the parent of the child, it's the society which is not untouched with it. Corporal punishment increases the use of violence in society and legitimizes it in the eyes of succeeding generations. It promotes a double standard: there are two categories of citizens' children and adults. It's acceptable to assault children, but not adults. Corporal punishment contributes to broken family patterns. Corporal punishment makes protection of the child difficult. Because the practice of corporal punishment is tolerated, children lose faith in society as a protective environment. It contributes to a society characterized by submissive citizenship, where individuals have learned from their earliest years that being a victim is a natural condition.

Alternatives to Corporal Punishment

An important technique in maintaining classroom control is to develop a milieu of effective communication and positive reciprocal relationships between parents, students, and teachers. School officials should possess expertise in child and adolescent development, generally enjoy working with children in the academic setting, have a strong desire to help youth learn, and promote an environment that clearly demonstrates that students are valued, respected, and understood. The emphasis should be on positive educational exchanges between teachers and students, not futile, contentious, win-lose contests. Students, as well as their parents, should be carefully involved in decision-making about school issues affecting them, including the development and implementation of educational goals and disciplinary rules, along with positive behavioral support where required. Schools should have peer support programs that utilize techniques to encourage acceptable behavior. It is critical that teachers receive adequate training and resources to help them effectively maintain classroom control without resorting to violent or aggressive techniques. One way to accomplish this is to provide teachers, both during pre-service and in-service training, with the ability

to employ behavior management techniques that promote pro-social classroom interactions among the students; this would also promote a positive learning environment for those students. Teachers who comprehend the deleterious short- and long-term consequences of corporal punishment may be motivated to make appropriate changes to their classroom management skills. Schools should have an ample supply of counselors in the school to help teachers provide their problem students with access to another caring adult who can promote self-management as well as anger and impulse control especially for younger children.

Relevant Constitutional Provisions

Article 21 of the Constitution of India which protects the right to life and dignity includes the right to education for children up to 14 years of age. Corporal punishment amounts to abuse and militates against the freedom and dignity of a child. It also interferes with a child's right to education because fear of corporal punishment makes children more likely to avoid school or to drop out altogether. Hence, corporal punishment is violative of the right to life with dignity.

Article 39(e) directs the State to work progressively to ensure that "... the tender age of children are not abused". Also, Article 39(f) directs the State to work progressively to ensure that "children are given opportunities and facilities to develop in a healthy manner and in conditions of freedom and dignity and that childhood and youth are protected against exploitation and against moral and material abandonment."

Till recently, the provisions of Sections 88 and 89 of the IPC were invoked to explain the power teachers exercised when inflicting corporal punishment. These two provisions in the chapter on 'General Exceptions' cover harms that may be caused without penal consequence. Further, India is a State Party to the Convention on the Rights of the Child. The standard of 'the best interests of the child' is now a part of domestic law. In 2006, the Committee on the Rights of

the Child explained this obligation further when it reiterated, in General Comment No. 8, “the right of the child to protection from corporal punishment and other cruel or degrading forms of punishment”.

In theory, corporal punishment is covered by all the provisions under Indian law that punishes

perpetrators of physical harm. While these provisions make no distinction between adults and

children, in practice, corporal punishment in schools and other institutions tends not to be prosecuted because it is widely accepted socially and regarded as legitimate. So the provisions highlighted in this section, the criminal provisions in particular, have the potential to be used in situations of corporal punishment, but rarely are.

Legal Basis:-

RTE Act, 2009 :- The Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education (RTE) Act, 2009, which has come into force with effect from 1 April 2010, prohibits ‘physical punishment’ and ‘mental harassment’ under Section 17(1) and makes it a punishable offence under Section 17(2). These provisions read as follows: 17. Prohibition of physical punishment and mental harassment to child – (1) No child shall be subjected to physical punishment or mental harassment.

(2) Whoever contravenes the provisions of subsection (1) shall be liable to disciplinary action under the service rules applicable to such person. Sections 8 and 9 of the RTE Act place a duty on the appropriate Government and the local authority to “ensure that the child belonging to weaker section and the child belonging to disadvantaged group are not discriminated against and prevented from pursuing and completing elementary

education on any grounds”. The RTE Act does not preclude the application of other legislation that relates to the violations of the rights of the

child, for example, booking the offenses under the IPC and the SC and ST. Prevention of Atrocities Act of 1989. The Juvenile Justice (Care and Protection of Children) Act, 2003. The Juvenile Justice (Care and Protection of Children) Act, 2000 is an important statute that criminalizes acts that may cause a child mental or physical suffering. As per Section 31.1 of the RTE Act the NCPCR and SCPCRs are supposed

to:

- (i) Examine and review the safeguards for rights provided by or under this Act and recommend measures for their effective implementation;
- (ii) Inquire into complaints relating to child’s right to free and compulsory education;
- (iii) Take necessary steps as provided under Sections 15 and 24 of the Commissions for Protection of Child Rights Act :-Under Section 32(3) and (4) of the RTE Act, the SCPCRs are the appellate authority to receive appeals from the aggrieved persons who would prefer such appeals when their grievances relating to children’s right to education are not redressed by the designated local authorities under Section .

Conclusion:-

Corporal punishment is a dark reality that routinely inflicts our daily lives but in a majority of cases it goes unnoticed and unreported on account of the innocence of the victim, stigma attached to the act, callousness and insensitivity of the investigating and the law enforcement agencies, etc. Merely enacting legislation will not be enough unless this is followed by strict enforcement of the law with accountability defined. Also, parents, teachers and others in the community have a vital role to protect children from various forms of exploitation and abuse. Children are the country’s greatest human resource and a measure of the country’s social progress lies in the wellbeing of its children: that they are healthy, educated, safe, and happy and have access to life opportunities. It is our duty that corporal punishment should be combated as early as possible. Besides government, many independent agencies and NGOs can work

together for the betterment of children. This will help both the countries shine bright and develop in a crime free way, as children are the leaders of tomorrow.

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